

IN SITU TENSILE OBSERVATION OF A SQUEEZE CASTING SiC WHISKER-6061Al COMPOSITE IN TRANSMISSION ELECTRON MICROSCOPE

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SUMMARY: The fracture process of a squeeze casting SiCw/6061Al composite has been observed using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) straining techniques. The results show that the crack initiation modes include: (1) cracking of the SiC whiskers; (2) decohesion of the SiCw-Al interfaces and (3) tearing of the matrix. The interaction between crack, dislocations and whisker has been examined in detail. The SiC whiskers in the SiCw/6061Al composite are major obstacles to the propagation of cracks. The SiCw/6061Al composite does not form the single major crack which results in the fracture of the composite, instead, the microcracks can only propagate and grow to a limited size. The failure of the specimen is caused by the abrupt linkage of cracks. A film of aluminum could be observed adhering to the exposed whiskers along the crack edge. This indicates that the SiCw-Al interfaces in the squeeze casting SiCw/6061Al composite is high strength bonded.

KEYWORDS: SiCw/6061Al composite, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) straining techniques, crack initiation, crack propagation, interaction between crack, dislocations and whisker

INTRODUCTION

Major restrictions on the application and dissemination of aluminum-matrix composite materials reinforced with SiC whiskers or particles have been their low ductility and fracture toughness. In recent years, its failure mechanisms have been studied by numerous investigations[1-4]. These mechanisms can be loosely grouped into four categories: (1) cracking of the whiskers or particles [1]; (2) decohesion of the SiC-Al interfaces; (3) fracture of the matrix [2,3] and (4) cracking of the precipitates and/or brittle particles in the matrix [4]. The dominant fracture mechanism of a SiC/Al composite depends on a variety of factors such as: (1) the composition of the matrix and the alloying element added; (2) the microstructure of the matrix; (3) the volume fraction, shape (short fibre, whisker, particulate and particle) and size of the SiC; (4) the spatial distribution of SiC; (5) the nature of the SiC-Al interfaces; (6) the fabrication technique and processing of the composite and (7) the heat treatment condition applied to the composite. Since the failure of a SiC/Al composite is influenced by so many factors and failure mechanisms mentioned above often coexist, it is difficult to categorize the fracture process in SiC/Al composite materials and to take effective measures to improve the ductility and toughness. Although the fracture process of SiC particle-Al (SiCp/Al) composites produced by powder metallurgy process have been extensively studied, related information on the squeeze casting SiC whisker-Al (SiCw/Al) composites is limited. The objective of the present paper is to investigate the fracture process

of a squeeze casting SiCw/6061Al composite using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) straining techniques. Compared with a previous work in which the initiation and growth of microcracks in a squeeze casting SiCw/99.75% Al has been examined in details [5], particular emphasis will be placed on the difference in fracture behavior of the SiCw/6061 from that of SiCw/99.75% Al.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The SiCw/6061Al composite was produced by a squeeze casting method. Using (-SiC whisker (of diameter 0.1~1.0 μm and length 30~100 μm) as the reinforcement and commercial 6061 aluminum alloy as the matrix. The volum fraction of SiCw is 23%. The TEM specimens were cut from as-cast billets and prepared by ion milling and then strained on the tensile stage in the TEM. The fracture process of the composite was observed in situ.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Crack Initiation

Figures 1(a), (b) and (c) are microcracks caused by the cracking of SiC whisker, the decohesion of SiCw-Al interface and the tearing of the matrix in the SiC clustering region, respectively. The crack initiation sources are the same as that in the SiCw/99.75% Al composite [5]. However, the microcracks caused by the matrix cracking in the SiCw/6061Al can only grow to a limited size rather than propagate and form the major crack which leads to fracture of the specimen as that in the SiCw/99.75% Al.

Interaction Between Crack, Dislocations and Whisker

As shown in Figure 1(c), a distinct dislocation-free zone (DFZ) is present between the crack tip and the inverse pile up. The size of DFZ in the SiCw/6061Al is much smaller than that in aluminum. This may be due to the suppressing effect of the SiC to the movement of dislocations. Cell wall are often observed adjacent to SiC whiskers during the TEM experiments, see Figure 2. When a crack approaches to a whisker, the propagation of the crack often stopped and a pile up of dislocations concurs between the crack and the whisker. This indicates that SiC whiskers play an important role in impeding crack propagation. On the other hand, it is obvious that the piling up dislocations in front of SiC whiskers will also lead to stress concentration.

Fig.1: Microcrack initiation sources: (a) cracking of SiC whisker; (b) decohesion of SiC-Al interface and (c) tearing of the matrix

Fig.2: Interaction between a crack, dislocations and a whisker; the crack advancing by bypassing the whisker end

Fracture Mode

In the early stages of straining, many microcracks could be detected mainly in the matrix adjacent to SiC whiskers and in the matrix in the SiC clustering regions. These microcracks could only propagate and grow to a limited size, as shown in Figure 3(a). The cracking processes of the ligament between cracks are sequentially shown in Figures 4(a), (b), (c) and (d). The ligament cracks by shear fracture, and there is no substantial neckin before fracture. An interesting phenomenon can be found from the sequential TEM micrographs that a distinct turing of the ligament is occurred, which may be due to the shear stress applied to the ligament. The fracture mode of the SiCw/Al is different from that of the SiCw/99.75% Al [5] and the unaged SiCp/6061Al [6]: (1) the SiCw/6061Al composite does not form the single major crack which leads to the fracture of the specimen; (2) the local strain of the ligament between cracks after fracture is much smaller than that in the SiCw/99.75%Al and (3) the failure of the specimen is caused by the quick linkage of cracks (see Figure 3(b)). There may be two interpretations. Firstly, it is easier to result in stress concentration for SiC whiskers than SiC particles, and the matrix adjacent SiC whiskers is easier to crack. Secondly, they are more difficult for the stress concentration to relax and for the crack to propagate for the SiCw/6061Al relative to the SiCw/99.75%Al due to higher yield strength and work hardening rate of the former than that of the latter.

Fig.3: Fracture mode of the SiCw/6061Al composite, (b) showing the failure of the specimen is caused by the abrupt linkage of microcracks in (a)

Fig.4: Sequential TEM micrographs showing fracture of the ligament between cracks

Fractured Surface

The TEM micrographs of the fractured surface in SiCw/6061Al composite are shown in Figure 5, in which (b) is at higher magnification than (a). A film of aluminum could

*Fig.5: TEM micrographs of the fractured surface in SiCw/6061Al composite.
(b) is at a higher magnification than (a)*

be observed adhering to the exposed whiskers along the crack edge. This indicates the bonding strength of the SiC-Al interfaces in the squeeze casting SiCw/6061Al is at least higher than the ultimate strength of 6061Al alloy. In addition, the quantity of the exposed whiskers along the crack path is far smaller than the average volume fraction of SiC whiskers

in the SiC/6061Al. This may be because that the formation of microcracks is dominated by the cracking of the matrix although there are three microcrack initiation sources detected as shown in Figure 1.

CONCLUSIONS

The SiCw-Al interfaces in the squeeze casting SiCw/6061Al composite is high strength bonded. The crack initiation modes include: (1) cracking of the SiC whiskers; (2) decohesion of the SiCw-Al interfaces and (3) tearing of the matrix. The SiC whiskers in the SiCw/6061Al composite are major obstacles to the propagation of cracks. The SiCw/6061Al composite does not form the single major crack which results in the fracture of the composite, instead, the microcracks can only propagate and grow to a limited size. The failure of the specimen is caused by the abrupt linkage of cracks.

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